

PEDAGOGICAL ETHICS: THE TEACHER'S RESPONSIBILITY AND ROLE IN SOCIETY

Qosimova Ozoda Xudoynazarovna

Uzbekistan-Finland Pedagogical Institute, associate professor of the "Pedagogy" department

Hamdamova Kamola Olimjon qizi

Student of Uzbekistan-Finland Pedagogical Institute

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Abstract: This article talks about the relevance of pedagogical ethics, the teacher's responsibility and role in society. The article analyzed the role of pedagogical ethics in the educational system, the importance of teachers' adherence to ethical norms in the educational process, and social results. Pedagogical ethics determines the responsibility of the teacher as an educator, not just a teacher, and has a great impact on the moral and personal development of the young generation. The article shows that the use of high moral values by teachers increases the social stability in the society and the efficiency of the educational system.

Keywords: Pedagogical ethics, teacher's responsibility, role in society, moral standards, education system, social stability, education, professional development, young generation, teacher's influence.

Pedagogical ethics is one of the most urgent issues in ensuring the effectiveness of the educational system today. By following moral standards in his activities, the teacher not only imparts knowledge to students, but also forms them as useful citizens for society. The relevance of pedagogical ethics lies in its ability to influence social and moral changes in society. Every teacher should teach moral values to his students, because it is important for the development of the young generation not only academically, but also morally and personally.

In today's global world, especially in the rapidly changing social and cultural environment, it is necessary for teachers to adhere to professional and personal ethical standards. The educational system is the force that forms the moral indicators of the society, and pedagogical ethics is the main guide in the relationship of the teacher in the society, in his family, and with his students. Also, paying attention to the moral ethics of teachers allows to prevent unpleasant situations in the educational process, not only to provide students with knowledge, but also to teach them social skills.

Pedagogical ethics is a system of moral principles and standards that a teacher must observe in the performance of his profession. Pedagogical ethics develops skills that enhance the professional work of the teacher, educate him scientifically and spiritually. Pedagogical ethics teaches the teacher to follow ethical criteria not only in teaching, but also in relationships with students. This directly affects the professional and personal behavior of the teacher. Pedagogical ethics and moral principles define clear guidelines for the performance of all duties of a teacher related to his work.

A teacher is not only a provider of knowledge, but also a person who directly participates in the moral and social formation of young people. His responsibility affects not only academic, but also personal development of students. In addition to imparting real knowledge to students, the teacher teaches them life skills, love of work, appreciation of justice, friendship and mutual respect. The teacher's responsibility

fully covers his personal behavior, educational activities and obligations to the society. In society, a teacher is valued as a person who respects his profession and follows moral rules. Also, the responsibility of the teacher to the students is very high, because he plays a big role in shaping their education and upbringing.

The role of the teacher in society is reflected not only in his role as a person who gives knowledge, but also as a social shaper. The teacher plays an important role in determining the future of society, its moral and social views. The professional activity of the teacher helps to form equality, justice, human rights and other social values in the society. The professional responsibility of a teacher depends not only on his activities in the classroom, but also his position in society and social participation. A teacher can make a difference in society through his students. They contribute to the overall development of the society by providing knowledge to the youth.

Pedagogical ethics includes moral standards that determine the professional behavior of a teacher. These standards determine how a teacher should behave toward students, parents, colleagues, and society. Teachers should accept values such as honesty, justice, mutual respect and love as the main principles in their work. Such ethics include the responsibilities of the teacher to teach students, to ensure fairness in education, and to respect the individual rights of students. The main principles of pedagogical ethics are listening, respect, mutual trust and fairness.

Also, pedagogical ethics makes a great contribution to the formation of the young generation. Teachers teach their moral values to the younger generation and develop their personal and social responsibilities. This helps to ensure justice, respect, mutual understanding and stability in society.

Pedagogical ethics, the teacher's responsibility and role in society are important factors that ensure the effective functioning of the educational system. Educators play a major role not only in imparting knowledge, but also in educating young people and forming them as useful citizens of society, making moral principles, justice, equality and respect the main principles in their work. Also, pedagogical ethics is important not only in the teacher's own activity, but also in the development of social stability and moral values in society.

The results of pedagogical ethics in society and the educational system have wide-ranging and long-term effects. A teacher's adherence to ethical standards leads to the following positive results:

- **Personal and professional development:** Pedagogical ethics helps teachers to continuously improve themselves in their professional activities, increase respect for their own standards and adapt to the changing educational environment. This, in turn, leads to an increase in the quality of education.
- **Educating the young generation:** Pedagogical ethics ensures the formation of young people on the basis of moral values, mutual respect and responsible relations. A teacher's adherence to high moral standards instills these values in students. This serves to ensure social justice and stability in society.
- **Community stability and social change:** Teachers' adherence to ethical principles helps ensure social stability and justice. The application of moral norms and values in the educational process has a positive effect on changes in society, helps prepare young people for important roles in society.
- **Social trust and respect:** Teachers' adherence to high ethical standards increases public trust in teachers. This increases public confidence in the education system, improves the quality of education, and creates better opportunities for students.
- **Positive relationship between teacher and student:** Pedagogical ethics develops positive and trusting relationship between teacher and student. These relationships help improve the effectiveness of the educational process, increase students' self-confidence, and motivate them to achieve better results.

In conclusion so to speak Pedagogical ethics is an important factor determining the teacher's responsibility and place in society. A teacher's adherence to moral standards increases the efficiency of the education system, plays a major role in educating the younger generation, and ensures social stability in society. Focusing on the professional and ethical development of teachers serves to improve the quality of the education system and contributes to the development of society as a whole.

List of references

1. Toshpulatov, M. (2020). *Pedagogik etika va ta'lim tizimidagi o'rni*. Toshkent: O'zbekiston Respublikasi Ta'lim vazirligi.
2. Karimova, N. (2019). *Pedagogik me'yorlar va o'qituvchining jamiyatdagi roli*. Tashkent: Ilm Ziyo.
3. Xusainov, A. (2021). O'qituvchining kasbiy etikasining yoshlarni tarbiyalashdagi o'rni. *O'zbekiston ta'limi*, 1(5), 33-42.
4. Xudoynazarovna, Q. O., & Qurbonovich-Dozent, U. U. (2022). DEVELOPMENT OF TEACHER'S SPIRITUAL IMAGE. *International Journal of Early Childhood Special Education*, 14(6).
5. Qosimova, O., & Jaxbarov, O. (2022). PEDAGOG XOTIN-QIZLAR SHAXSIGA QO'YILADIGAN PEDOGOGIK PSIXOLOGIK TALABLAR. *Gospodarka i Innowacje.*, 22, 643-645.
6. Khudoynazarovna, K. O., & Ulugbek, M. (2022). TOLERANCE AS AN IMPORTANT MORAL CATEGORY. *International Journal of Intellectual Cultural Heritage*, 2(2), 148-152.
7. KHUDOYNAZAROVNA, K. O. (2022). THE TECHNOLOGY OF ORGANIZING EDUCATIONAL ACTIVITIES FOR THE FORMATION OF THE PERSONAL SPIRITUALITY OF THE FUTURE TEACHER. *International Journal of Philosophical Studies and Social Sciences*, 2(3), 278-287.
8. KHUDOYNAZAROVNA, K. O., SEVARA, K., & RUKHSORA, M. (2022). STUDYING THE PSYCHOLOGICAL BASIS OF NATIONAL CONCEPT OF PERSONALITY. *International Journal of Philosophical Studies and Social Sciences*, 2(3), 265-271.
9. Касимова, О. Х. (2023). Роль Женщин И Девушек-Педагогов В Развитии Мышления Молодежи. *Research Journal of Trauma and Disability Studies*, 2(12), 389-392.
10. Касимова, О. Х. (2023). Повышение Социальной Активности Женщин-Учителей–Веление Времени. *Research Journal of Trauma and Disability Studies*, 2(12), 393-396.
11. Daniyarovna, H. S. (2022). The didactic model of activating students' independent work. *Spectrum Journal of Innovation, Reforms and Development*, 4, 303-307.
12. Xudoynazarovna, Q. O., & Qurbonovich, U. U. (2022). A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE MAIN MOTIVATIONS FOR INCREASING THE QUALIFICATION OF TEACHER-WOMEN AND TEACHER-MALE. *International Journal of Early Childhood Special Education*, 14(3).
13. Utanov Utkir Qurbonovich, X. L. A. qizi . (2023). THE ROLE OF MUSIC IN MEDICINE AND THE ISSUES OF ITS INFLUENCE ON HUMAN PSYCHOLOGY AND HEALTH. *INTERNATIONAL BULLETIN OF APPLIED SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY*, 3(6), 297–300. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8019314>
14. Utanov Utkir Qurbonovich, A. A. A. (2023). MODERN REQUIREMENTS FOR THE ORGANIZATION OF MUSIC CLUBS IN GENERAL SECONDARY SCHOOLS. *INTERNATIONAL BULLETIN OF APPLIED SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY*, 3(6), 94–97. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8019320>
15. U.Utanov. (2023). THE USE OF ANCESTRAL HERITAGE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE TEACHER'S SPIRITUAL IMAGE. *JOURNAL OF AGRICULTURE & HORTICULTURE*, 3(6), 95–100. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8055288>